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A Creative Folio

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From Novice to Expert: A Voyage towards Mastery

A fresh graduate, a newly registered nurse,
At the starting line, unsure which path to traverse.
After the board exam, joy and excitement abound,
But once the thrill fades, new questions resound.

“What’s next? Where to apply? How do I begin?”
Anxiety grows when no mentor steps in.
Days pass in doubt, yet courage takes hold,
An application submitted, a new story unfolds.

Hired at last, but new worries arise,
“Can I be a good nurse? Will I meet the ties?
Can I deliver the care, fulfill what’s expected?
Will colleagues accept me, will I be respected?”

These questions linger, but eagerness shines,
Through learning and practice, confidence aligns.
A novice nurse grows with each passing day,
Experience and training light up the way.

Being a novice is no cause for shame,
It’s a vital phase in the nursing game.
For learning brings wisdom, and wisdom will show,
That novices blossom, and experts will grow.

In time we master the art of our field,
With wisdom, knowledge and skill, our future is sealed.
From novice to expert, the journey is clear,
A path of growth, courage, and cheer
and a voyage towards mastery is here.